

RAMI: RAdiomics for LGE Assessment of Myocardial Infarction and Microvascular Obstruction

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Background: Late gadolinium Enhancement (LGE) is the method of choice for assessing myocardial infarction (MI) and viability, which can be used to guide revascularization decisions [1-4]. LGE can also predict functional recovery revascularization. Moreover, dark no-reflow regions (or microvascular obstruction) within the LGE-enhanced areas, where blood flow remains inadequate post-revascularization, have been associated with worse clinical outcomes [5]. Automatic segmentation and classification methods mainly focus on regions of LGE uptake and do not address areas of no-reflow [6,7]. Radiomics has become popular for automatic quantitative feature extraction [8,9], which can potentially help identify diseased tissues. Here, we propose two radiomics models based on LGE features to improve MI diagnosis and detect no-reflow.

Methods: 100 patients (33 normal, 67 pathological, including 40 with no-reflow) from the EMIDEC Phase Sensitive Inversion Recovery (PSIR) dataset [10], consisting of 5-10 short-axis slices, were used. The dataset was split into training (70%), used to optimize the models through a 4-fold cross-validation process, and held-out test (30%) sets while maintaining stratified proportions. The first RAdiomics model for Myocardial Infarction detection, RAMI, was constructed using logistic regression with elastic net regularization and image features extracted from myocardium segmentation. The second model, RAMI-NOR, was developed using a random forest that specifically targeted the identification of MI with NO-Reflow by considering image features extracted from MI segmentation. Elastic net regularization was used to avoid overfitting. SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) analysis was used to explain model outputs.

Results: RAMI exhibited excellent performance, achieving an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) of 0.99 ± 0.02 and 0.95 on the cross-validation and held-out test, respectively. It demonstrated a remarkable sensitivity of $100\% \pm 0\%$ on both sets and specificities of $90\% \pm 17\%$ and 100% , respectively. RAMI-NOR, designed to identify MI cases with no-reflow, yielded lower AUC values of 0.76 ± 0.10 on the cross-validation and 0.71 on the held-out test. Regarding sensitivity, this model achieved $83\% \pm 17\%$ on the cross-validation and 70% on the held-out test. Specificity values were $79\% \pm 27\%$ and 73% , respectively. Figures 1-3 show model flowcharts, confusion matrices, SHAP plots, representative cases featuring segmentations and radiomics maps.

Conclusion: This study demonstrates the potential of RAMI, a highly accurate logistic regression model, to automatically distinguish normal and pathological cases based on LGE radiomics features. RAMI-NOR has shown promise for assessing MI cases with no-reflow, but still requires further refinement or exploration of alternative deep learning-based methods for addressing the more challenging cases.

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by: “la Caixa” Foundation and FCT, I.P. under the project code [LCF/PR/HR22/00533]; FCT through projects UIDB/04326/2020 (DOI:10.54499/UIDB/04326/2020), UIDP/04326/2020 (DOI:10.54499/UIDP/04326/2020) and LA/P/0101/2020 (DOI:10.54499/LA/P/0101/2020).

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Figure 1. Flowchart of the RAMI and RAMI-NOR Radiomics-based models for Myocardial Infarction (MI) diagnosis and no-reflow detection, respectively. For RAMI, MI diagnosis model, myocardium segmentations were used to extract radiomics features, which were subsequently utilized to train a logistic regression model. The RAMI-NOR model relied on radiomics features extracted from segmentations of the MI area to train a random forest for identifying cases with no-reflow. To enhance model explainability, SHAP analysis was used to obtain the most important features of each model. Then, radiomics feature maps of those features were obtained to demonstrate differences between positive and negative cases.

Figure 2. RAMI and RAMI-NOR Models: confusion matrices and SHAP analysis results for the held-out test dataset. (A) Confusion matrix of the RAMI model on the held-out test dataset (0 – normal case; 1 – myocardial infarction, MI); (B) RAMI model SHAP beeswarm plot of feature importance (the most important feature was the correlation feature from gray-level co-occurrence matrix – glcm). Other glcm, gray-level dependence matrix - gldm, shape, and first-order features were among the most important features; (C) Confusion matrix of the RAMI-NOR model on the held-out test dataset (0 – MI without no-reflow; 1 – MI with no-reflow); (D) RAMI-NOR model SHAP summary plot of feature impact on the model output (the feature with most impact on the model output was the Maximal Correlation Coefficient, MCC, from glcm). Other glcm, gldm, gray-level run-length matrix, shape, and first-order features were among the features impacting the model the most.

Figure 3. LGE images, segmentations, and radiomics maps for 3 representative cases. (A) LGE image of a normal case; (B) LGE image of a myocardial infarction (MI) case without no-reflow; (C) LGE of a MI case with no-reflow; (D-F) Corresponding myocardium segmentation in yellow; (E-F) MI in red; (F) and no-reflow in blue. (G-I) Gray-level co-occurrence matrix (gcm) correlation radiomics maps, represented with Full-Rainbow CLUT, for (A-C) cases, respectively. Both MI cases, (H) and (I) exhibit fewer purple areas and more green areas than the normal case (G). (J-K) gcm Correlation and Maximal Correlation Coefficient (MCC) radiomics maps, represented with Full-Rainbow CLUT, for the MI case without no-reflow (B) and with no-reflow (C). In (J), the area corresponding to the MI - red region in (E) - is predominantly purple and blue, while the region of MI + no-reflow in (K) - red and blue regions in (F) - is predominantly red. This demonstrates the importance of this feature for the discrimination of MI cases with and without no-reflow.